

Linguistics unambiguously proves that the homeland of the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily was in the eastern part of Eurasia

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Abstract

Linguistics proves that the homeland of the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily was somewhere in the territory of South-Western China. If language X contains fossilized forms whose structure cannot be understood through the material of language X, and these forms are well explained through the material of language Y, it suggests that language Y is either ancestral to X or is closely related to the ancestor language of X. In Sumerian, Hattic, and North-Caucasian languages, there are fossilized forms whose structures are opaque and which can be explained through the material of Yeniseian languages, Sino-Tibetan languages, and Ainu. This suggests that the languages of the Eastern branch of the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily are closer to its proto-language, and that the proto-language of the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily was located somewhere in the eastern end of Eurasia, supposedly in the territory of South-West China.

Keywords: Ainu language; Sino-Tibetan languages; Ainu-Minoan stock; Sino-Caucasian family; comparative linguistics

1. Introduction to the problem

The Ainu-Minoan macrofamily is a variant of the Sino-Caucasian (Dene-Caucasian) macrofamily. The Ainu-Minoan macrofamily consists of the following languages and language families: Ainu, Great Andaman, Sino-Tibetan, Nivkh, Yeniseian, Northeast Caucasian, Sumerian, Northwest Caucasian, Hattic, Minoan (see: Akulov 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021a, 2021b, 2022, 2025; Akulov, Nonno 2024; Desherieva 2026; Nonno 2025a, 2025b, 2025c).

When they speak about the localization of the homeland of the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily they usually place it somewhere in the Middle East region. The hypothesis that the ancestral home of the Sino-Caucasian macrofamily was located in the western part of Eurasia is not based on an analysis of linguistic material, but is essentially an uncritical transfer of the concepts of the origin and dispersal of humanity presented in the Abrahamic religions.

Linguistics clearly and unambiguously shows that the spread of languages of the Ainu-Minoan (Sino-Caucasian) macrofamily went from the east of Eurasia to the west, and not vice versa. The exact location of the homeland of this macrofamily is debatable, but in our opinion it was somewhere in the territory of south-western China (Fig. 1).

2. Linguistics alone, without any help of other sciences, is able to completely resolve the question of homeland of a certain family

Let there are two languages: X and Y which are related, i.e.: belong to the same family.

If language X contains fossilized forms which structure cannot be understood or analyzed using only the material of language X, and these forms are well explained using the material of language Y, then this indicates that language Y is either ancestral to X, or language Y is close to the ancestor language of X.

For example, in language X we see a word which structure is completely opaque, while in language Y we see a phrase from which the opaque word of X was derived, and in this phrase the meaning of all components is clear and transparent. It is perfectly clear that language Y is ancestral to X or close to the ancestor of X.

The transformation of phrases and entire sentences into individual words is a normal and natural process while the reverse process – the unfolding of words into phrases and sentences – is completely improbable. The transformation of fully meaningful words into auxiliaries and then into affixes has been well documented across a wide variety of different languages. The transformation of affixes into fully meaningful words is never observed anywhere. If we understand which language is ancestral to another, we immediately understand the overall picture of migrations.

3. Fossilized forms in Sumerian, Hattic and North Caucasian and their Yeniseian, Sino-Tibetan and Ainu prototypes

In the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily, we can see that, for example, in the Sumerian, Hattic, and in North Caucasian languages, there are fossilized word-forms, the structures of which are opaque if we use only the material of the corresponding languages, but which can be analyzed using the material of Yeniseian, Sino-Tibetan languages, and also the material of the Ainu language.

3.1. Sumerian *pap/pab* "father"

In Sumerian, there is a word *pap* meaning "father"/"male" (ePSD 2024). The structure of the word *pap* is completely opaque if we use only the Sumerian language. But if we look at the Yeniseian languages, we see a word like *b-op* "my father" where *op* is "father," and *b-* is a possessive marker for the first person singular (Werner 1997).

3.2. Hattic word *pin/pinu* "child", "son"

In the Hattic language there is the word *pin/pinu* "child" or "son"¹. Using only Hattic material, it is impossible to understand the internal structure of this word. The Hattic word-form *pinu* is related to the Proto-Yeniseian forms **pu-b* "son"² and **pu-n* "daughter"³. However, suffixes *-b* and *-n* in Proto-Yeniseian are fossilized, unproductive, and their meanings are unclear.

¹ Soysal 2004: 301.

² Starostin 2005i.

In Proto-Sino-Tibetan there are such forms as **Pǎ* "man"⁴ and **nrǎH* "woman"⁵, that is, suffixes that in Proto-Yeniseian are fossilized, unproductive, but in Proto-Sino-Tibetan they are full-fledged normal words.

Then, the component **pu*, which is present in Proto-Yeniseian word forms, corresponds perfectly to Proto-Sino-Tibetan **pōk* "child"⁶ and also to Late Jōmon Ainu – **po* "child"⁷. Thus, the form **pu-b* literally means "child-man" or "little man" and **pu-n* means "child-woman" or "little woman".

3.3. Proto-West-Caucasian **pəχ^wA* "daughter"

In Proto-Northwest Caucasian, the word for "daughter" is reconstructed as **pəχ^wA*⁸. This form contains the root *χ^wA*, which derived from the Proto-North Caucasian word-form **qwǎnV* "woman"⁹.

The prefix **p(ə)-* is considered as one of the so-called formal prefixes with an unclear meaning attached to nouns in Proto-Northwest Caucasian.

the Proto-North Caucasian word-form **qwǎnV* correlates well with Proto-Yeniseian form **qVm* "woman"¹⁰.

And the Proto-Yeniseian form **qVm* is well explained through Proto-Tibeto-Burman word-forms: **ka*¹¹ **mow*¹² "my woman". It is noteworthy that such forms exist in modern languages, for example, in Lepcha *ku-mo* "lady"¹³, in Qiang *qu-pu* "my spouse"¹⁴, in Ainu¹⁵ *ku=mat* "my wife".

Proto-Yeniseian **qVm* is a contraction of a form close to the form **ka-mow*. And the 'mysterious' prefix **p(ə)* correlates well with the Proto-Yeniseian form **pəń-* "small"¹⁶, which perfectly correlates with the Proto-Sino-Tibetan **pōk* "child" and with the Ainu word form *pon* "to be small"¹⁷ and with Late Jōmon Ainu – **po* "child".

4. Conclusion

Thus, it is quite obvious that within the Ainu-Minoan macrofamily the ancestor of the languages of the Caucasian cluster separated from the languages of the Yeniseian cluster, therefore, both the Proto-Yeniseian and the historical Yeniseian languages retain features that are ancestral to the languages of the Caucasian cluster. In its turn, the ancestor of the entire

³ Starostin 2005g.

⁴ Starostin 2005d.

⁵ Starostin 2005f.

⁶ Starostin 2005c.

⁷ Akulov, Nonno 2024: 17.

⁸ Starostin 2005a.

⁹ Starostin 2005b.

¹⁰ Starostin 2005j.

¹¹ Matisoff 2015a.

¹² Matisoff 2015b.

¹³ Wikipedia 2026.

¹⁴ LaPolla, Huang 2003: 50.

¹⁵ Ainu is a relic of Proto-Dino-Tibetan (Proto-Tibeto-Burman), see for instance Akulov, Nonno 2024.

¹⁶ Starostin 2005h.

¹⁷ Batchelor 1905: 353.

western branch of the Aino-Minoan family separated from the Sino-Tibetan cluster (the western branch of the Aino-Minoan macrofamily includes Yeniseian, Caucasian languages, Sumerian, and also Hattic with Minoan). Therefore, in the Proto-Sino-Tibetan and in the historical Sino-Tibetan languages are preserved the ancestral forms to the forms existing, in the Yeniseian languages.

Fig.1. A map representing the history of spread of the main languages of the Aino-Minoan stock across Eurasia

Also, it is important to note that population genetics without the help of other sciences is not able to answer the question "who stood on whom". Anthropologists and historians who rely on genetic data, in particular, on haplogroups, usually come to a dead end and throw up their hands when they see that people belonging to the same linguistic macrofamily represent completely different genetics: Y haplogroups D and O are quite wide-spread among peoples speaking Sino-Tibetan languages, while the Y haplogroup J is quite frequent among the people of the South-West of Eurasia and in particular among the peoples of the Caucasus. And the Yeniseians and Native American people demonstrate a fairly high frequency of haplogroup Q.

The answer here is very simple: no ethnicity is in any way determined by genetics; the entire history of mankind clearly testifies it. Ethnicity is determined solely by language. When the

discourse is about contacts of populations, about migrations, then data of genetics are helpful, but they should be linked first if all with the data of linguistics.

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